

Quantum Wavefunction and Fluctuation of Classical Action Part III

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In Part I of this note, we argued that d/dX Action (where Action = Integral dt L, L being the Lagrangian) for a particle with constant velocity is p whether the classical $L = .5mv^2$ or the relativistic $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) is used. Thus, a fluctuation or error of δX leads to a change of $(\delta X) p$ in the Action. We tried to argue that this led to the form $\exp(ipx)$.

In this note, we revisit this scenario. We argue that if one wishes to have a constant error due to a fluctuation/error in X in the Action regardless of p , then $\delta x = 1/p$ is a characteristic length. At first one may expect a relative error to be of interest, but we argue that a potential may knock a particle from one p value to another. In such a case, it may be useful to have the error, and not the relative error, remain constant. Thus, one already has a wavelength, but this suggests a periodic function to describe the error of the action throughout space, and there are many possibilities. A periodic function may have positive and negative values corresponding to positive and negative X fluctuations in a regular way. We ultimately argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is ideal and is also linked to spatial density through $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$. Thus, we argue that two ideas are involved. First, the idea of an error/fluctuation in the Action is used to develop the idea of a wavelength. Secondly, one tries to find a periodic function associated with the wavelength which is also linked to spatial density. Finally, one tries to generalize these ideas to the nonrelativistic case of potential present. This seems to present a statistical picture.

Classical Action and the Idea of a Wavelength

One may take the relativistic or nonrelativistic Action for a particle with constant velocity, written as $v=X/T$, and vary it with respect to X (independently of T) to obtain:

$$d/dX \text{ Action} = p \quad ((1)).$$

The relativistic Lagrangian is $-m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) and the nonrelativistic, $.5mv^2$.

For a photon, we consider $H=E= pc-L$ with $c=X/T$. Then: $L=E-X/T$ and the action is:

Action = $ET-pX$ which matches the results for the particle case.

Thus, for a fluctuation of δX , ((1)) suggests a change in the Action of $p \delta X$.

(One may note that the Action is used to derive Lagrange's equations/ Newton's second law.)

If one wishes the fluctuation/error due to a change in X in the Action to be the same for all p , then a characteristic length emerges equal to $1/p$. At first, one might think that a relative error may be more appropriate i.e. $p \delta X / (TL)$. We argue that if a potential is present and one considers a statistical scenario i.e. momentum distribution in which one p is knocked into

another p_1 value, then the wavelength changes from $1/p$ to $1/p_1$, but the error in the free particle Lagrangian remains constant.

Given a characteristic length, it seems that one may seek a periodic function with the argument px . Many periodic functions exist, so it is not clear which to use.

A fluctuation in the Action is linked to energy. Changing X , however, seems to involve spatial density changes too. The particle travels with constant $v=X/T$ yet a fluctuation/error in X changes this smooth motion. Perhaps one may find a periodic function which carries the wavelength, is linked to energy, but at the same time to spatial density. A particle moving with constant velocity has the same probability to be at any x point. A periodic function $\exp(ipx)$, however, has a modulus of 1 which might link it to $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

Thus, it seems that one considers fluctuations $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and seeks a factor which renders this constant. $\exp(-ipx)$ satisfies this condition. If p changes to p_1 , one argues that the spatial density is not constant.

Finally, one has a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ describing an error/fluctuation in the Action due to a fluctuation/error in X where $v=X/T$. This holds for a particle moving at a constant velocity. With this choice:

$$-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = pp \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, the curvature of this statistical type $\exp(ipx)$ (linked to spatial density of the free particle) is related to kinetic energy.

It is interesting to note that the free particle moves with a constant velocity and has equal density to be at any x and yet is associated with a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ with wavelength $1/p$ which may have positive and negative (real values due to positive/negative X fluctuations) and whose curvature is linked to pp i.e. to kinetic energy.

Addition of a Potential

For a classical particle, a potential introduces force and accelerates/decelerates a particle. In a statistical scenario, like a classical gas, one has free particles at each point x . A particle which does not collide another accelerates from one x point, but in the statistical picture one separates out time and does not follow such an acceleration. There is only a density change from one x to another.

One may try to apply a similar scenario to the quantum picture. There is only one particle, but if a potential is present (which is the driver of interactions), one might consider an ensemble of free particles at each x i.e. a probability momentum distribution. Then,

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

A knock from one p to another p_1 changes the wavelength, but not the error/fluctuation of the free Action. An important question is whether $W^*(x)W(x)$ is still linked to spatial density and whether $-d/dx d/dx W = pp W$. In ((3)), $a(p)$ is unknown, so one may force the second condition:

$$E - V(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad ((4))$$

This yields a set of $a(p)$ values, but only for discrete E values if appropriate boundary conditions are applied. Why are boundary conditions an issue? For the classical non-statistical picture, one has a particle which decelerates reaching a velocity of 0 at a turning point. For a statistical ensemble, there is no time hence no deceleration. There is only an ensemble $W(x)$ at the turning point. How does one link this ensemble to spatial density to force it to die down rapidly at the turning points?

((4)) shows that the curvature of $W(x)$ may be forced to yield classical kinetic energy at x i.e. $E - V(x)$. $W(x)$ itself is an average of various free particle Action fluctuations due to X fluctuations, each with a weight $a(p)$. If one considers $W^*(x)W(x)$, then:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_{p1, p2} a^*(p1)a(p2) \exp(-ip1x) \exp(ip2x) \quad ((5))$$

We argued above that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ yielding a constant spatial density, but that $\exp(-ip1x)\exp(ip2x)$ would yield a density due to different fluctuations in the classical Lagrangian for $p1$ and $p2$. Integrating over all space, however, eliminates all such cross terms, but local densities may be affected. This seems to be critical to establishing dropping $W(x)$ values outside of x classical turning points. The quantum oscillator is an example of this. Thus, the periodic nature of the error/fluctuation of the Action leads to positive and negative values with a periodicity of $1/p$ which are crucial to allowing interference (positive/negative cancellations) which reduce the value of $W(x)$ (real) outside x classical turning points.

Two Slit Interference

Just as one considers an ensemble of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms at each x which may interfere, one may consider an ensemble of x values for the same p (i.e. multiple slits). In such a case, one obtains an interference pattern. In this case, the different x values are lengths from each slit to the same point on a screen (or to a detector). The slits should be separated about the length $1/p$ as this is the characteristic error/fluctuation length associated with a fluctuation in the Action due to X .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that periodicity with a wavelength of $1/p$ follows from setting the error/fluctuation of the classical Action for a particle with constant $v=X/T$ with respect to X constant for all p . This condition allows for stochastic hits from a potential to change a $p1$ to $p2$ without changing the fluctuation error of the Action. A periodic function is then sought which has links to spatial density because ΔX fluctuations should be linked to density even though one does not see any such changes for a freely moving particle. This suggests $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. Such a choice shows that $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to spatial density while its curvature is linked to kinetic energy.

By choosing a periodic function linked to spatial density probability, one introduces a statistical scenario. In classical physics, such a scenario, even in the presence of a potential $V(x)$, contains a momentum distribution of free particles at each x with varying density. We suggest a similar scenario for the quantum situation i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$.. One may force the curvature of $W(x)$ to be linked to classical kinetic energy i.e.

$$E - V(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$$

This leads to discrete E if appropriate boundary conditions are chosen i.e. a dropping spatial density outside of classical x turning points. Thus, $W(x)$ must be directly related to spatial density. We propose that $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{spatial density}$ just as $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ represents spatial density for a free particle. Interference of $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms is critical for causing $W(x)$ to drop rapidly outside x turning points. A statistical bound system does not have visible acceleration, only free particles at each x , so their density must mimic the effects of a particle being stopped at a turning point. (The statistical picture, however, allows for tunneling through the barrier unlike a strict classical turning point.)